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Review Article

A Review on Herbal Shikakai Shampoo

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ABSTRACT

Shampoo is one of the beautifying agent. It is a cosmetic type product using surfactant as the main compound which when used under the specified condition will remove surface grease. (6) The herbal shampoo was prepared by using bahera, amla, hibiscus, neem, Tulsi, alo-vera, fenugreek, evaluated for organic powder characteristic from test dirt dispersion test, surface tension management. The herbal shampoo is a natural product. The herbal shampoo not only cleanses the hair but also provides conditioning, smoothing, and overall hair health, ensuring the absence of dandruff, grease, and lice. (23,24) Various drugs are used for the mixture of cosmetics shampoo. This in present work we found good properties for the herbal shampoo and further optimization study benefits of herbal shampoo on human used as beautifying agent. The study aimed to formulate a pure shikakai shampoo and to evaluate and compare its physicochemical properties with the marketed synthetic and shikakai shampoo. The formulated shikakai shampoo wash also evaluated for condition performance by administering a blind test to 20 student volunteers. The formulated shikakai shampoo wash clear and appear.

INTRODUCTION

Hairs are the integral part of human. Hair is also a crown for humans for those reason hair require special care to keep it shily smooth difficult to broken and easy to combed. (6,8)

Different shampoo formulations cater to various hair type care habits and specific issues like oily hair, dandruff and androgenic alopecia.

Herbal medicine has come become more and more popular recently because of all of their benefits

Herbal shampoos are the cosmetic preparations that consist of traditional and ayurvedic herbs which are meant for cleansing the hair and scalp just like the regular shampoos. (6)

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Herbal shampoo is probably widely used cosmetic products for cleansing hair and scalp in our daily life herbal shampoos are the cosmetic preparations that with the use of traditional ayurvedic herbs are meant for cleansing the hair and scalp just like the regular shampoo. ⁽¹⁾

This leaves the hair too dry to handle or comb. Hence proper conditioning of the hair is also an important consideration some shampoo cause irritations to the eye and a lasting corneal cloud.

Scientific innovation and the art of improving one's personal beauty and well-being are expert combined in the broad field of cosmetic science.

This area of study clarifies the producer that transform raw material into composition that enhance visual beauty by delving into the intricate chemistry biological chemistry technology manufacturing cosmetic

Cosmetic are not only used to modify appearance of an individual but are also used care of skin and body there are various types of cosmetics available with specific and significant purpose.

The creative self-expression and self-identify aspect are considered to be the key factor which contribute to the fame of cosmetic in correct scenario. ⁽²⁸⁾

The traditional south Asian herb shikakai is well known for its advantageous effect on skin and hair care. ^(18,19,20)

The objective of this project is to develop an herbal shampoo that promotes hair growth enhance strength smoothness adds shine and restores natural hair colour without causing any damage. ^(2,3,4)

Herbal Shampoo

Shampoos are most probably used as beautifying it is a hair care product that is use for cleanse scalp and hair in our daily life.

The purpose of using herbal shampoo is used to remove dirt that is make up on the hair without stripping out much of the sebum. the purpose of using herbal shampoo is used to remove dirt that is make up on the hair without stripping out much of the sebum.

The herbal shampoo is better in performance & safer than the synthetic shampoo herbal shampoos are totally natural no any other ab Delhi. Bohot dur chemical is added.

They are large number of medicinal plants which are beneficially effect on hair and are commonly used. ⁽¹⁾

Objective:

The objective of using shampoo can be summarizes as follow

- 1. Cleansing action:** shampoo serves the primary purpose of cleansing the hair removing dirt oil and other impurities accumulated on the scalp and stand.
- 2. Oil Removal:** shampoo helps to eliminate excess oil from the hair preventing in from appearing greasy or weighed down.
- 3. Nutrient delivery:** some shampoos are formulated to deliver essential nutrient to the hair such vitamins minerals and proteins. These ingredients can help nourish and strengthen the hair stand.
- 4. Texture improvement:** shampoo can contribute to improving the texture of the hair making it smoother softer and more manageable.
- 5. Darkening hair colour:** certain shampoo may contain ingredients that can darken or

enhance the natural colour of the hair providing a subtle change in shade. ⁽²³⁾

Advantage:

The advantage of using herbal shampoo include

- 1. Pure and Organic Ingredient:** herbal shampoo is formulated with pure and organic ingredients derived from nature without the use of synthetic chemical.
- 2. Less Side Effect:** due to their nature composition herbal shampoo are generally associated with fewer side effects compared to shampoo containing artificial ingredients.
- 3. Skin Friendly:** herbal shampoo is designed to be gentle and nourishing to the scalp and skin.
- 4. Cost-effect:** while prices may vary, herbal shampoo can often be cost-effective in the long run. ⁽²⁴⁾

Disadvantage:

- 1. Difficult to hide odour and taste.** Due to the use of natural ingredients, herbal shampoo may have a distinct odour and taste that can be challenging to mask completely.
- 2. Slower Effect and long-term therapy:** herbal drugs generally have a slower onset of action compared to allopathic drugs.
- 3. Sensitivity to scalp:** some herbs used in herbal shampoos like menthol can be sensitive to certain individual scalps. ⁽¹⁵⁾

History-Indian subcontinent

In the Indian subcontinent, a variety of herbs and their extracts have been used as shampoo since ancient times.

Human hair: A very effective early shampoo wash made by boiling sapindas with dry Indian gooseberry (amla) and selection of other herbs using the strand extract and. ⁽³⁰⁾

Hair problem

Split ends occur when the oil from the scalp does not reach the ends of the hair; it tends to dry and split over time, and another reason is heat from styling tools.

Fig-1- split ends of hair

Dandruff is the scaly particle that at the root of the hair is dandruff, which is caused by poor hygiene, dry scalp, infection, excess sebum, and sensitivity to certain products. It is a harmless, non-inflammatory skin condition that affects the scalp and can lead to hair loss. ⁽²⁸⁾

Fig - 2 - Dandruff problem hair

Regular coloring sessions can damage the hair in the long run. The chemicals in the dye can also cause dryness, dandruff, breakage, and split ends. Medicated shampoo, extra care conditioning, and nourishing can treat damaged hair.

Fig- 3 - Hair Colour Damage

Hair loss occurs due to several factors such as stress hormonal imbalance and using the wrong products. Prevention is possible by using protein food food switching to mild shampoo massage with hot oil staying hydrates and exercise regularly.

Fig – 4 - Hair loss problem ⁽²⁸⁾

Part of the Hair

Dermal papillae: the dermal papilla is responsible regulating the hair cycle and hair growth and also comprised of androgen receptors that are sensitive to the presents of DHT

Matrix: the matrix surrounds the dermal papillae and contains all the active seeded for hair growth for the development of the different parts of the hair particularly the outerrootsheath the inner root sheath and the hair shaft ⁽¹⁾

Figure

Ideal properties of herbal shampoo

- It should be easily removed on rinsing with water.
- It should leave the hair non- dry soft shiny with good manageability minimum fly away.
- It should impart a pleasant perfume to the hair.
- It should not cause any reaction / irritation to skin or eye. ⁽²⁸⁾
- It should not make the hand rough and chapped.

USE OF INGREDIENTS

1) Soap Nut Extract

- Stops hair fall
- Prevent dandruff
- Fight against scalp infection ⁽¹⁾

Fig-1-Soap-Nut

Soap nut extract from the fruit of the sapindas mukorossi tree is increasingly used in herbal shampoo due to its natural cleansing properties and skin benefits

1. Natural Surfactant: soap nut extract contains saponins which act as natural surfactants. This allows it to effectively remove dirt oil and impurities from the hair and scalp without stripping surfactants.

2. Moisturizing Properties: soap nut extract is known for its moisturizing effect helping to keep the hair hydrated. (12,13)

3. Scalp health: the antimicrobial properties of soap nut extract can help maintain scalp health by combating dandruff and other scalp conditions.

Its natural antifungal and antibacterial properties can reduce itchiness and irritation.

2) Amla extract

Family: Euphorbiaceae

Biological source: *Emblca officinalis* Gaerth

- Prevent or treat fungal and bacterial hair scalp infections
- Reduce hair loss.
- Stimulate hair growth.
- Prevent or treat dandruff and dry scalp.
- Improve overall appearance. ⁽¹⁾

Fig – 2 - Amla

Amla is widely used in shampoos due to its numerous benefits for hair health.

Nutrition support: Amla is rich in vitamin c essential fatty acid and other nutrients that nourish hair follicles promoting healthy growth. ⁽¹⁶⁾

Dandruff control: Amla possesses anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties that can help alleviate dandruff and soothe an irritated scalp.

Natural conditioning: Amla as a natural conditioner improving hair texture making it softer and shinier and scalp.

Strengthening hair: helping to detangle hair. ⁽¹³⁾

3) Shikakai extract

Family: Fabaceae

Biological source: Dried pods of *Acacia concinna*

- Prevent grays
- Add more shine to the hairs.
- Cleanses hair. ⁽¹⁾

Fig – 3 - Shikakai

Shikakai derived from the pods of the acacia concinna tree is a popular ingredient in herbal shampoos due to its numerous benefits for hair.

Natural Cleansing Agent: shikakai acts as a natural cleanser due to its saponin content which helps remove dirt and excess oil from scalp without stripping hair of its natural moisture

Promote Healthy Hair Growth: shikakai rich in vitamin A C D E and K which nourish hair follicle and promote healthy hair growth. Its use in shampoos can help strengthen hair and reduce hair loss.

PH balancer: Shikakai has a low PH which helps maintain the natural acidity of the scalp and hair promoting overall hair health. This balance is essential for preventing dryness and damage. ^(11,12)

4) Aloe vera

Family: Asphodelaceae

Biological source: Dried latex of aloe-vera leaves

- a. Deeply clean oily hairs.
- b. Promote hair growth.
- c. Smooth natural curls. ⁽¹⁾

Fig-4-Aloevera

Aloe vera extract is a popular ingredient in shampoo and hair care product due to its numerous beneficial properties.

Moisturizing properties:

Use: aloe vera is known for its hydrating properties helping to retain moisture in the hair and scalp.

Shooting Irritation:

Use: aloe vera can help soothe an irritated scalp and reduce inflammation making it beneficial for those with sensitive skin. ^(11,12,13)

5) Reetha

Family: Sapindaceae

Biological Source: Dried fruits of Saprindus mukorossi

Sapindus mukarossi sapindaceae, soapnuts is also called as arishtak in ayurveda and soap nut tree in India. It is well known for traditional medicinal uses as a hair cleanser.

Fig – 5 - Reetha

Uses

Reetha is responsible for the production of foam and for anti-foaming effect so it used in herbal shampoo for foam production in the shampoo.

It is generally used as a cleansing and production of foam in the shampoo.

Hence is important ingredient that are used in the formulation of herbal shampoo. (2,3)

6) Methi

Family: Fabaceae

Biological source: Dried ripe seeds of *Trigonella foenum-graecum*.

These seeds are a staple in every Indian kitchen. Its seeds are high in vitamin A, C, K protein and folic acid making it the best ayurvedic medicine. Fenugreek seeds contain the protein nicotinic and which is effective against hair loss, dandruff and other scalp issues.

Fig – 6 - Methi

Uses

Reduce hair fall:

Methi contains protein and nicotinic acid which strengthen hair roots and reduce hair fall.

Control dandruff:

Both shikakai and methi have antifungal and antibacterial properties that help reduce dandruff and itchy scalp.

Gentle cleansing:

Shikakai in natural cleanser that removes dirt and oil without stripping natural moisture.

7) Neem

Family: meliaceae

Biological Source: the biological source of neem is the *Azadirachta indica* tree which is native to India subcontinent and parts of southeast Asia.

Uses: Neem is a common ingredient in herbal shampoo. because it promotes the hair growth. neem leaves contain quercetin and beta-sitosterol which contain anti-bacterial and anti-microbial properties which provide protection from fungus that causes dandruff.

Fig-7-Neem

It also contains flavonoids, tannin, phenols, saponin, azadirachtin, and gallic acid and also contains vitamin E. All these chemical constituents are found in neem that promote hair loss and also reduce the dandruff in the scalp.

In neem, tannin and are present that play an important role in the formulation of herbal shampoo because it promotes antifungal activities as well as contains anti-inflammatory activity.

Neem is a rich source of vitamin E which help repair damaged cells. ⁽⁵⁾

8) Rose oil

Rose oil particularly rose essential oil can be a voluble ingredient in shampoo due to numerous beneficial properties. Here are some key uses and benefits.

Fig -8 -Rose oil

Uses:

1) Moisturizing property:

Rose oil can help hydrate the scalp and hair preventing dryness and promoting overall hair health.

2) Anti-inflammatory effect:

Rose oil can soothe an irritated scalp which may help reduce conditions like dandruff and itching. ⁽¹²⁾

Evaluation of herbal shampoo

The prepared formulation underwent evaluation for product performance including assessment of organoleptic characteristics PH level physiochemical properties and solid content.

Dirt dispersion: two drops of the shampoo are added to a test tube containing 10 ml of distilled water.

Visual assessment: colour of prepared shampoo is evaluated for its colour the colour is checked visually. Odour: odour is found by smelling the product.

PH determination: the of prepared herbal shampoo in distilled water 10%v/v is evaluated by mean of ph. analyzer in the room temperature ^(16,17)

How can shikakai in hair care routine ⁽³⁰⁾

1	Shikakai shampoo	With the help of natural shampoo cleanses and Nourishes your hair. Shampoo without Parabens help heal severely damage hair reduce frizz.	
2	Shikakai hair mask	Mask promotes elasticity and luster while providing the hair with deep nourishment.it hair fall and stops hair breaking.	

3	Shikakai hair oil	Natural herbs Support as treatment of many hairs issue is added to this natural hair oil.	
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MATERIALS AND METHOD

Collection of material: ⁽²⁹⁾

TABLE : Detail of the plant material study

Sr	Common name	Botanical name	Parts used	Category
1	Hibiscus	Hibiscus rosa-sinensis	Flower	Conditioning agent
2	Amla	Embolic officinalis	Fruit	Anti-dandruff agent
3	Shikakai	Acacia concinna	Powder	Detergent
4	Soapnut	Sapindas indica	Fruit	Detergent
5	Cassia	Cassia auriculata	Leaves	Antidandruff agent
6	Bring raj	Eclipta prostrate	Leave flower	Hari growth
7	Aloe vera	Aloe barbadense	Leaf	Copland

Material

Material	Quantity
Reetha extract	2.5 g
Amla extract	2.5 g
Shikakai extract	2.5 g
Sidr extract	2.g
Neem extract	2.5 g
Methyl problem	1ML of 0.05% solution
Gelatin solution	q.s
Citric acid	q.s
Essential oil	0.1 mL

Type of shampoo

Shampoos are of following types given below

- liquid herbal shampoo.
- lotion shampoo
- powder shampoo
- solid gel shampoo
- medicated shampoo
- clear liquid shampoo
- conditioning shampoo

- anti-dandruff shampoo
- cream shampoo
- traditional shampoo
- herbal shampoo
- Baby shampoo ⁽²⁹⁾

Benefits of herbal shampoo

- less hair loss
- remove dandruff
- long lasting colour
- promote hair growth
- All-natural no chemical
- keep healthy natural oils
- more shine

Function of hair shampoo

- lubrication
- conditioning
- hair growth
- maintenance of hair colour

- medication ⁽²⁹⁾

Uses of Shikakai Shampoo

Promotes Hair Growth:

It strengthens hair roots and helps in reducing hair fall clean and dandruff-free.

Prevents Dandruff:

Its antifungal and antibacterial properties help keep the scalp

Condition The Hair:

Shikakai acts as a natural conditioner making hair soft shiny and smooth.

Prevent Dryness and Itching:

Its smoothness the scalp and reduce irritation or dryness.

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

Nowadays our new generation facing lot of problem-like hair fall itching in scalp irritation dandruff problems. ⁽⁷⁾ The purpose of this review article is to raise awareness among individuals about the potential of traditional plant in hair care treatment. Herbal shampoo is safer than synthesis shampoo. The PH of the shampoo was adjusted to 5 to retain mantle of scalp which is acidic there is a strong need to change the consumer of a good shampoo and the onus lies with formulations. ⁽²⁹⁾

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